

SYNTHESIS OF SiC-WHISKERS VIA SOL-GEL TECHNIQUE IN THE BULK OF SiC COMPOSITE

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Keywords: *SiC, composite, matrix, sol-gel, carbothermal synthesis*

Introduction

Development of new specimens of state-of-the-art technology, particularly aviation technology, is closely associated with advancement of materials science, development of new structural materials and coatings which can be applied in harsh environment (at elevated temperatures and under mechanical loading). Intensive studies of characteristic properties of nanosized particles have shown that their introduction into structural materials even in small amount allows improving crack resistance (which is crucial for high-temperature ceramic materials) and modifying other properties of practical importance.

Silicon carbide is one of the key compounds used for production of structural ceramic and composite materials for high-temperature applications due to the unique combination of properties such as low density, high decomposition temperature, absence of phase transitions in a wide temperature range, good mechanical properties, inertness to many corrosive media, and the highest oxidation resistance among refractory carbides. Its preparation in highly dispersed state considerably extends fields of application, including decrease in energy consumption during production of SiC-based articles at lower temperatures, more effective application of slip technique, and development of conceptually new processes for production of materials [1-5].

Synthesis of nanocrystalline silicon carbide using sol-gel technique to obtain highly dispersed starting mixture “SiO₂ – C” is extremely promising and rapidly growing line of research. There are various approaches which considerably differ from each other, primarily, in the type of precursors. For

example, the following disperse forms of carbon can be used as carbon source:

- soot;
- carbon nanotubes – single-layer and multilayer;
- colloid systems “disperse medium – nanographite”;
- nanosized diamonds, and so on.

The following compounds are used as silicon source in different methods: silica sols and silicon alkoxides, especially, tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) [6-14].

There are also methods utilizing polymeric compounds (primarily, phenol-formaldehyde resins) as carbon source.

Thus, one of the promising techniques of SiC production is the hybrid method which involves sol-gel synthesis of superfine, reactive and uniformly distributed starting mixture “SiO₂-C” by means of controlled hydrolysis of tetraethoxysilane in the presence of polymeric source of carbon (phenol-formaldehyde resin LBS-1) and the subsequent carbothermal reduction at moderate temperatures (below 1500-1600°C), which was used by the authors to obtain ultra-refractory carbides [15-21].

One of the important advantages of this method is the possibility to prepare highly dispersed particles of the target products as nanocrystalline powder, thin films, and also as superfine matrixes directly in the bulk of the composite since sol-gel transformation due to hydrolysis occurs for some time making it possible to impregnate porous materials.

The goals of this work are the following: study dedicated to the influence of the starting mixture “TEOS – polymeric source of carbon – acid

catalyst– water” composition on the time of formation of slow-flowing gel; synthesis of fibrous silicon carbide directly in the bulk of porous SiC material (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Diagram for synthesis of superfine SiC directly in the bulk of SiC material using sol-gel technique

Experiment, Results and Discussion

Investigation of gelation during tetraethoxysilane hydrolysis in the presence of polymeric source of carbon

One of the specific features of the sol-gel technique, applied in this work for production of superfine, reactive starting mixture “SiO₂-C” (further used for

carbothermal synthesis of fibrous SiC) directly in the bulk, is the possibility to obtain, depending on the task, both functionally-graded materials and materials with uniform volume filling. Therefore, it is necessary to make additional experiments on effect of the concentration of hydrolysis catalyst (formic acid) on the time of formation of high-viscous systems. Studies were performed using rotational viscometry (Fungilab Smart L apparatus, spindle L2). Measurements of dynamic viscosity of solutions were made at shear rate 100 rpm, and at temperature 60±5°C. Ratio of silicon- and carbon-containing reagents was 1:3 for all experiments. Molar ratio TEOS:H₂O (1:3) was also maintained. Volume of reacting system and concentration of all reagents were maintained by means of variation in the solvent (acetone) content. Viscosity measurements were finished upon reaching 300 cP. It may be inferred from the obtained data (Figure 2) that concentration of hydrolysis catalyst (formic acid) makes a substantial influence on the gelation time.

Fig. 2. Dependences of dynamic viscosity on time and n(Si):n{CHO(OH)} ratio

The viscosity versus time curves are similar for all experiments – for a long period (30-37 minutes) viscosity of colloid systems changes insignificantly, after which increase in dynamic viscosity occurs for

5-6 minutes up to 50 cP. Further increase in dynamic viscosity takes place in an avalanche for 1-2 minutes.

Thus, the determined time conditions for the formation of slow-flowing gels (from 37 to 46 minutes), probably, make it possible to impregnate porous SiC composites in full.

Appearance of the prepared gels is shown in Figure 3.

According to the IR spectroscopy of the xerogels prepared as a result of multistage drying at temperatures in the range 70-140°C in vacuum drying box and at a residual pressure about 100 mm Hg), the weak stretching band of OH-groups occurs in the 3100-3700 cm^{-1} region for all three compositions, which may correspond to the Si-OH fragments, OH-groups of ethanol, formic acid and water, incorporated into the xerogel structure. In addition, the absorption bands at 1550, 1610 and 1710 cm^{-1} were observed, corresponding to C=O and C=C groups of phenol-formaldehyde resin, formic acid and acetone. There is a strong broad band with shoulder at 1050-1300 cm^{-1} , which results from the overlapping of C-O, C-C and Si-O stretching bands. It should be noted that in the 800-820 cm^{-1} region both gel and xerogel spectra contain the absorption band characteristic for condensed Si-O-Si fragments, formed as a result of TEOS hydrolysis and polymerization.

As a whole, IR spectra are completely identical for all three experiments. This allows us to make a conclusion that xerogels contain the same functional groups. Thus, variation in the hydrolysis catalyst content has no influence on the chemical nature of the prepared xerogels.

Fig. 3. Appearance of silicon&carbon-bearing gel with Tyndall cone which gives proof to the formation of the disperse system

The obtained xerogels were used for synthesis of superfine starting mixture "SiO₂ – C" by means of thermal treatment of xerogels at a temperature of 450°C under dynamic vacuum (the residual pressure lies in the range $\sim 1 \times 10^{-1} \div 1 \times 10^{-2}$ mm Hg).

The specific surface area for powders after sample degassing at 300°C was determined by BET method (low-temperature nitrogen adsorption, T = 77 K, Autosorb-1 apparatus). The specific surface area S was calculated to be 190.8 m^2/g based on weight-change data processing. Such big value of S is additional proof of the formation of nanosized particles combined into nanostructured agglomerates with mesopores.

Additional experiments allowed determining the specific surface area related to the micropores (38.0 m^2/g) and the external surface area (152.8 m^2/g).

The average radius of mesopores, obtained as a result of automatic processing of experimental data, was found to be 12.365 Å.

Fig. 4. Microstructure of the obtained superfine starting mixture in accordance with SEM data

According to the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) data (triple-beam workstation NVision 40 from Carl Zeiss with attachment for energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis from Oxford Instruments), no separation of silicon dioxide and carbon phases was observed after thermal treatment of xerogels (Figure 4); size of agglomerates is less than 100 nm.

It is evident from surface mapping for a microparticle of the starting mixture, made on carbon, oxygen and silicon (see Figure 5) using EDX analysis, that distribution of these elements is uniform (the above-mentioned elements are present at all points of micrograph, with the resolution being equal to $\sim 1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}$).

Quantitative assay for carbon and silicon dioxide, as well as examination of the thermal behavior of the starting mixture in air, were made using differential thermal analysis (integrated TG/DSC/DTA analyzer SDT Q-600). The experimental conditions: temperature range 20-1400°C, air flow, heating rate 20°/min, gas flow rate 100 ml/min, average weight quantity 30-40 mg. Weight loss, started at a temperature of ~580°C, was observed up to a temperature of ~1200°C; the registered weight loss corresponds to the specified “SiO₂ – C” mole ratio, the deviation is less than 1.5%. Weight loss of the sample, probably, results from elimination of carbon located on the material surface and in closed pores of the material. This is supported by two partially overlapping exothermic effects on a thermogram with maximums at temperatures about 680°C and 794°C.

According to the performed test studies, the starting mixtures “SiO₂ – C”, obtained using the above-mentioned procedure, allow producing superfine silicon carbide under dynamic vacuum at temperatures of 1200-1300°C, and under inert gas (Ar) – at temperatures above 1550°C.

Synthesis of SiC-whiskers in the bulk of SiC composite

Impregnation of porous SiC-based materials (open porosity 39-42%, dimensions 80x8x5 mm – see Figure 5) with the starting mixture, containing TEOS, polymeric source of carbon (bakelite lacquer LBS-1), formic acid and water, was made under dynamic vacuum (~8-10 mm Hg) and at temperatures of 50-60°C during 15-30 minutes.

Fig. 5. Appearance of porous SiC cages (Federal State Unitary Enterprise “All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Aviation Materials”)

Then the samples were left in a reaction vessel for gelation, dried using several stages at temperatures of 70-150°C, and carbonized at temperatures of 750-850°C under argon. The last operation consisted in carbothermal reduction at temperatures of 1570-1600°C (3 hours).

The described operations were repeated until absence of weight loss after impregnation.

Optical microscopy data for the sample surface suggest that texture change (compaction) is observed after filling of pores with silicon carbide.

According to the results of XRD analysis, the samples contain the mixture of hexagonal and cubic phases of silicon carbide.

Microstructure of the sample cleavage in its bulk, obtained using SEM, is shown in Figure 6.

Generation of the layer of nanostructured globular particles on the surface of coarse particles, forming the starting material, is typical of the samples. There is a growth of one-dimensional particles (fibers) in the bulk of pores. Most of the one-dimensional particles are characterized by less than 50 nm in diameter and 200-400 nm in length, but there are also crystals with diameter ~70-150 nm and more than 2-3 μm in length. Relative position of these aggregates also generates three-dimensional cage-like structure. Based on the phase contrast mode, one can conclude that the bulk of the material doesn't contain impurities of any other phases. It should be noted that there is a large fraction of free pores which might be filled with the reinforcing phase.

Variation in the conditions of impregnation, gelation and high-temperature synthesis allows changing micromorphology of the formed particles.

The formation of extensive monocrystalline SiC fibers (see Figure 7) 80-100 nm in diameter and at least 10 μm in length (i.e. diameter-to-length ratio is at least 100-125) was registered in the bulk of the samples in a number of cases. Figure 7 illustrates in more detail the starting segment of monocrystalline fiber. As may be seen from the Figure 7, the main part of the whisker is the faceted crystal, and the whisker's top contains conic section on which nanocrystals of the other phase are concentrated.

Detailed investigation of the bulk structure of the samples before and after filling of their pore space with nanostructured silicon carbide was performed using computerized X-ray microtomography (SkyScan-1172 microtomograph).

Fig. 6. Microstructure of the pore bulk for SiC composite after modification using sol-gel technique

Exposure of the SiC-based composite sample was made in three stages:

- 1) At the first stage the sample was examined as a whole with resolution of $6.2 \mu\text{m}$ (the main exposure parameters: filter – aluminum foil 0.5 mm, X-ray tube voltage – 59 kV, X-ray tube current – $167 \mu\text{A}$, rotation angle – 0.4° , the number of accumulations per point – 10).
- 2) Then investigation of the zoomed-in piece of the central segment of the sample with resolution of $1 \mu\text{m}$; the main exposure parameters: no filter, X-ray tube voltage – 100 kV, X-ray tube current - 100 μA , rotation angle – 0.3° , the number of accumulations per point – 15.
- 3) Re-examination of changes in microstructure of the zoomed-in piece of the central segment of the sample was carried out after its saturation with the highly dispersed phase at resolution of $1 \mu\text{m}$ (the exposure parameters at this stage were identical to those for the previous experiment).

Fig. 7. Microstructure of SiC monocrystal (a) including microstructure in the phase contrast mode (b), SEM

The results of the first exposure stage lend credence to the view that the sample has the uniform structure, which is evidenced by the uniform density distribution (with resolution $> 1 \mu\text{m}$) indicated by distribution of light level. Study of the sample at the first stage (with resolution about $6 \mu\text{m}$) allowed obtaining survey X-ray plain sections of the overall sample and revealing possible macroscopic defects. It was stated that there were no large defects, voids and inclusions in the bulk of the starting sample.

At the second stage exposure was performed with resolution of $1 \mu\text{m}$, making it possible to examine in more detail the structure of void space of the sample before filling of pores, visualize it and estimate its statistical characteristics. Figure 8 presents the X-ray plain sections of the sample.

A local cubic region with the edge of 0.5 mm was used for calculation of the statistical characteristics, while a cube with the edge of 0.25 mm was used for development of the void space model in the bulk of the sample. To develop the model combining the void space model and the solid matrix of the sample, a cube with the edge of 0.125 mm was used.

Fig. 8. X-ray plain sections of the sample under study in three planes (total field of exposure is 4000 μm)

The three-dimensional (3D) model (see Figure 9) was developed using mathematical analysis, where location of pores in a cube with the edge of 0.25 mm was indicated by grey color.

Fig. 9. 3D model of the void space of the sample before pore filling with highly dispersed silicon carbide; a cube with the edge of 0.125 mm

Fig. 10. 3D model of the void space of the sample after pore filling with highly dispersed silicon carbide; a cube with the edge of 0.125 mm

Table 1 – Geometry features of the sample’s microstructure before and after partial filling of pores with superfine silicon carbide

PARAMETER	The value before pore filling	The value after pore filling
Volume within which the calculations were made, μm^3	125250000	127210000
Total porosity, %	23.0070	15.6150
Total volume of pores, μm^3	28815000	19865000
Open porosity, %	22.6260	13.7350
Volume of open pores, μm^3	28337810	17472600
Surface area of open pores, μm^2	18666900	13511400
Closed porosity, %	0.4924	2.1801
Volume of closed pores, μm^3	477190	2392400
Surface area of closed pores, μm^2	624970	2216300
Number of pores isolated from the sample surface	13754	18012

Similar exposure (resolution of 1 μm) was made at the third stage for the sample modified by highly dispersed silicon carbide. It allowed studying in more detail the void space structure of the sample,

visualize it and estimate its statistical characteristics after partial filling of pores. Figure 10 demonstrates the 3D model of the void space.

Table 1 lists the statistical data for the void space of the sample under study before and after its modification by highly dispersed silicon carbide.

Analysis of the obtained data and their comparison with open porosity values, determined by means of acetone impregnation method, suggest that both large pores (equal to or more than 1 μm in diameter), detectable by computerized X-ray tomography, and smaller pores were filled due to application of low-viscous starting systems.

Conclusion

Good prospects of application of the hybrid method for synthesis of nanocrystalline silicon carbide were demonstrated. The method consists of the following steps: sol-gel hydrolysis of tetraethoxysilane in the presence of polymeric source of carbon to form gel; multistage drying; carbonization of the system at moderate temperatures with the formation of superfine, reactive and uniformly distributed “SiO₂ – C” mixture; carbothermal synthesis for creation of the reinforcing matrix in the bulk of SiC ceramic material.

It was shown that variation in the concentration of the hydrolysis catalyst (HCOOH) could result in the formation of slow-flowing gel (300 cP) for 37-46 minutes. It should be noted that substantial change in the system viscosity, which can hamper impregnation during modification of a ceramic material, occurs during the last 7-9 minutes. For the first 30-37 minutes viscosity of the colloid system is close to the initial value; therefore, it can be used for filling of pores of the base material.

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